

***In vitro* development of magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate crystal by single diffusion method and study of its antimicrobial activity**

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Abstract : Struvite or magnesium ammonium phosphate hexahydrate (MAPH) is one type urinary stone that are which occur due to the urinary tract infection. These stones are mainly caused due to the bacteria which splits urea. These stone develop rapidly to form "Staghorn calculi" that causes urological disorder which is very painful. In this method, sodium metasilicate (SMS) act as a substrate for development of struvite crystal *in vitro*. The crystal is developed using single diffusion technique which consist of inner and outer reactant. After the growth of struvite crystals, they were dissolved in various solvents like DMSO, DMF and ethanol (at 50 ppm, 100 ppm, 200 ppm, 300 ppm). The dissolved compounds underwent the antimicrobial activity with *Escherichia coli*, *Acetobacter spp* and *Pseudomonas spp*.

Keywords : Struvite, Staghorn calculi, single diffusion method, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Urinary calculi is a very common and highly recurring painful urological disorder¹. The developments of the struvite stone are mainly due to urease splitting bacteria which cause urological disorder which is very painful²⁻⁴. Struvite stones are formed in urine at an alkaline or neutral pH condition. A small amount is lodged in the urinary bladder and urethra and leads to urinary tract infection. Urinary stone are also due to physical and chemical changes. During the formation of struvite stones the organisms hydrolyse ammonia and make the urine condition to neutral pH⁵.

The crystal can be grown *in vitro* by different techniques and the most prominent one is gel growth technique⁶. There are two types of gel growth technique namely single diffusion method and double diffusion method⁷. In this work single diffusion method has been used for the development of crystal since it provides the simple model for *in vitro* study⁸. *In vitro* crystal has been developed by using silica gel as a matrix substrate. The inner and outer reactant reacts in the above said matrix to start the crystal growth⁹.

It is necessary to inhibit the growth of struvite crystals. The study deals with identifying different micro organisms which can inhibit the growth of struvite crystals. Hence after developing the crystal, it is dissolved and is

tested for antimicrobial activity¹⁰ with different cultures like *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas spp*, *Acetobacter spp* and *Staphylococcus aureus* by using the well diffusion method.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

Sodium meta silicate (Sigma-Aldrich), ammonium dihydrogen phosphate (Sigma-Aldrich), magnesium acetate (Sigma-Aldrich), double distilled water, Muller hinton agar, agar-agar, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas spp*, *Acetobacter spp*.

Growth of struvite crystals :

The struvite crystals are grown by single diffusion technique. The preparation of stock solution was done by mixing 100 g of sodium metasilicate tetrahydrate with 250 ml of double distilled water for a specific gravity 1.03 g/cc. The inner reactant of 0.5 M ammonium dihydrogen phosphate was added to the stock solution to make its pH to 7.2. After gelling, the outer reactant of 1 M magnesium acetate was added to it. The crystal growth started observing after 36 h onwards.

Dissolving the struvite crystal :

The struvite crystal was separated by filtering method and was allowed to dry. Later the crystal was crushed using mortar and pestle. The powdered crystals were dis-

solved in 5 ml of solvents like DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide), DMF (dimethylfurone), THF (tetrahydrofurone), ethanol and acetone. These dissolved solvents were used for the antimicrobial sensitivity test with different concentrations such as 50 ppm, 100 ppm, 200 ppm and 300 ppm.

Preparation of MHA :

Muller hinton agar (MHA) was weighed for 21.6 g and agar agar weighed for 20 g, these were dissolved in 600 ml of distilled water. They were autoclaved at 121 °C at 15 lbs pressure for 15 min. At hand bearable condition the media was poured into 9 sterile petri-plates and they were set aside for solidification.

Antimicrobial activity :

After solidification each agar plates was scrapped with the respective cultures like *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Echerichia coli*, *Pseudomonas spp* and *Acetobacter spp* by immersing sterile cotton swab in the bacterial suspension and then rotate and compress against the wall of test tubes so as to rinse the excess fluid and 1 plate was maintained as control. Each plate was then cut with 5 wells using cork borer or well cutter and were added with dissolved crystal solvents at specific concentration such as 0.05 ml, 0.1 ml, 0.2 ml and 0.3 ml. In each plate 1 well was maintained as control with no dissolved solvents in it. All the plates were replicated and incu-

bated for 24 h at 37 °C. They were examined later for the zone of inhibition.

Results and discussion

The crystal is successfully developed using single diffusion technique as shown in Fig. 1. The crystal growth initializes in the gel solution interface where first both the reactants interact. The crystal developed will move towards different depths in the test tube. The crystal has grown to a maximum of length 2 cm.

The crystalline natures of the developed crystals are confirmed using X-Ray Diffraction Technique (XRD). The XRD pattern of the developed crystal is shown in Fig. 2. The peaks of the XRD pattern are compared with

Fig. 1. The struvite crystal grown using single diffusion technique.

Fig. 2. The XRD pattern of developed crystal.

JCPDS data and confirmed the presence of magnesium, ammonia and phosphate and hence the developed crystal is confirmed to be struvite.

The developed crystal structure is confirmed by using the optical microscope. The image obtained by optical microscope is given in Fig. 3. The developed crystal shows different morphologies like needle shaped, rectangular platelet, cubic etc.

Fig. 3. The optical images of the developed struvite crystal.

The antimicrobial activity on struvite crystals were studied to study the effect of micro-organisms in inhibiting the growth of the crystals. The study showed an inhibitory zone of 12 mm in *Staphylococcus aureus* at

Fig. 4. Inhibitory zone formation for (a) *Escherichia coli* and (b) *Staphylococcus aureus*.

concentration of 0.1 ml in the solvent DMF and 10 mm in *Escherichia coli* at concentration of 0.05 ml in the solvent ethanol. The inhibitory zone formation is shown in Fig. 4.

Conclusion

The struvite crystals were successfully developed *in vitro* and were characterized using X-Ray diffraction technique and optical microscope imaging. The antimicrobial activity is done for the developed struvite crystal. It was successfully found that the microbes namely *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Echerchia coli* form an inhibitory zone for the developed crystal.

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